

Estelar

Effective Substation TEchnoLogies for
Advanced viRtualization

Virtualising the future of substations

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PROJECT GOALS

 Digital Substation of the Future		
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PHYSICAL SUBSTATION

VIRTUALISED SUBSTATION

DIGITAL TWIN

TWO DEMOS

Virtualization
Testing Laboratories

IMPACT

Grant Agreement No. 101192574

Funded by
the European Union

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Pioneering Virtual Substations for a Climate-Neutral Future

 [/estelar-project/](https://www.linkedin.com/company/estelar-project/)

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